
When Control Succeeds but Discernment Fails: Preparing for AI-Assisted Safety Research

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Abstract

AI systems are increasingly used to accelerate AI safety research, yet our ability to reliably judge the correctness of their outputs—a capacity we term **discernment**—may not be keeping pace. This paper introduces the ‘discernment gap’: the growing difficulty experts face in catching subtle but critical errors in AI-generated safety research. We argue that this gap poses a significant risk, since AI **control** mechanisms can prevent harmful actions but do not guarantee technical correctness of outputs. This fuels a feedback loop in which perceived control success masks accumulating flaws, eroding risk management. We argue this scenario warrants urgent preparation and recommend (1) empirical testing to measure the discernment gap, (2) enhancing transparency and auditing of safety cases, and (3) strengthening human oversight as necessary complements to AI control.

Road-map: We (i) distinguish behavioural control from content discernment, (ii) show how success in the former can mask failure in the latter, and (iii) propose governance measures that close the gap.

1. Introduction: The Discernment Gap and System Stability

In the quest for safe advanced AI, several leading frontier AGI labs have expressed hopes to “automate alignment” as a load-bearing element in their development plans (Anthropic, 2023; OpenAI). Some techniques include the scalable-oversight paradigm (Bowman et al., 2022) which relies on human feedback for reward modeling and dataset

curation, alongside developing *AI control* techniques to constrain the outputs/actions of powerful systems even if alignment is imperfect (Greenblatt et al., 2023). Scalable oversight techniques are applied to two distinct goals in the model lifecycle: (1) during training, to improve the reward signal for alignment, and (2) during deployment, to enable the safe use of models by evaluating the truthfulness of specific outputs. This paper focuses on the challenges of the latter. *Control* mechanisms target the prevention of overt harmful actions like subversion or ‘scheming’ (Balesni et al., 2024). Their appeal is partly being more tractable for near-term implementation - by improving safety using existing techniques, even with overtly misaligned models.

It is critical to distinguish two types of failure.

Control aims to prevent behavioral failures, like an AI taking overtly harmful actions such as subversion or deception.

Discernment, however, addresses content failures, where a behaviorally-controlled AI produces plausible but subtly incorrect outputs. This paper’s central argument is that success in the former provides little assurance against the latter, and this is especially problematic when using AI systems to assist with AI safety research.

For instance, an AI system might propose a novel interpretability technique with mathematical proofs that appear valid but contain subtle errors in their assumptions about neural network behavior - errors that might only become apparent when applied to more capable future systems.

Over-reliance on AI systems for safety research may make it harder to ensure the safety of more capable future systems, with insufficient understanding to adequately perform risk management (ISO, 2018). The growing reliance on AI for safety research, combined with uncertain human evaluation capacity, requires early governance intervention before a substantial dependence is created.

Iterative deployment paradigms (OpenAI) favors frequent iteration cycles, where issues are detectable within the limits of human (and organization) reaction time. However, exponential progress and discontinuous capability jumps such as GPT-3 to GPT-4 (OpenAI et al., 2023) in AI development suggest such a process may be overwhelmed,

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Figure 1. Control tries to catch harmful actions, while potentially missing subtly flawed model outputs. These outputs may later be used (as part of AI-Assisted Safety Research) in safety mitigations for future, more dangerous models

where attempts at timely interventions can easily be either premature or too late (Bostrom, 2014).

AI progress may yield autonomous systems highly capable at software-engineering / ML before 2030 (Kwa et al., 2025), or sooner (Kokotajlo et al., 2025)¹. In such a future, control techniques might be relatively effective at detecting and preventing harmful AI system actions despite inadequate alignment. *Control* is already being explored by frontier AI providers (Grosse, 2024; Shah et al., 2025, p. 10) and is easier to develop with relatively short iteration cycles, compared to techniques for scalable oversight² such as debate, yielding positive but not yet sufficiently robust results³. Given this, robust techniques beyond *control* may not be ready in time.

1.1. Core Argument & Contribution

Our contribution is twofold: (1) framing the discernment gap as an urgent challenge to effective AI risk management, reducing detectability of failures - thus diminishing stability from a systems-theoretic perspective (Leveson, 2019), and (2) highlighting the specific challenges to discernment in the

¹Some forecasts are much longer, potentially 30 years. However, the *precautionary principle* suggests to take near forecasts seriously

²The author does not wish to imply that current AI control techniques make it easy to achieve high safety guarantees - in fact, in agentic settings control now faces new and difficult engineering challenges (Bhatt et al., 2025). Instead, the main thing pointed out is that it has shown more progress compared to scalable oversight

³See Appendix B for current state and projected maturity timeframes for different techniques

domain of AI-assisted safety research, not sufficiently addressed by standard robustness advancements. Importantly, *behavioural control* does not ensure detectability of *content failures*; hence discernment remains essential.

1.2. Related Concepts to Discernment

Evaluation gap: a shortage of tests relative to AI capabilities progress (Hobbhahn, 2024).

Weak overseer: a non-expert overseer may give incorrect reward signal, if supervising an advanced AI system, or have insufficient time to provide detailed oversight of each training example (Amodei et al., 2016).

Judge accuracy: an empirical metric in debate experiments (Irving et al., 2018).

While related to these concepts, *discernment* as used here refers to the ability to distinguish correctness. It tries to capture the challenge of evaluating technical correctness in domains where ground truth is contested—distinct from both general evaluation difficulty and reward-signal quality. It relates closely to *research taste*.

2. Analogy: Shifting from Inherent Stability to Active Control

AI control assumes a *misaligned* model, and aims to prevent catastrophic outcomes from *scheming* via defensive protocols such as monitoring and output filtering (Greenblatt et al., 2023), as well as more sophisticated techniques in an agentic setting (Bhatt et al., 2025). However, assessing

correctness of an AI output may be more difficult than preventing scheming, and has not been substantially addressed by *control* protocols in current research (see Section 3.1 for more detail).

Crucially, control protocols in current research (Greenblatt et al., 2023) focus on preventing deceptive or harmful behaviors, not on ensuring **technical** output correctness. A model could pass all control evaluations—never attempting to deceive or subvert—while still producing subtly flawed technical work.

Figure 2. Analogy comparing the inherent stability of passenger planes (akin to current chatbots via the *inability* safety case) to unstable fighter jets (representing future Agents or more advanced AI requiring active control)⁵

2.1. Analogy - Fighter Jet

Current systems are largely safe by default, relying on *inability* safety cases (Goemans et al., 2024) where they inherently lack the capability to produce unacceptable outcomes in terms of cyber-offense, CBRN, or loss of control⁶.

Consider a modern fighter jet. Contrary to passenger planes, a jet is by design aerodynamically unstable - requiring constant corrections from a control system simply to fly in a straight line. This design yields better agility (Nguyen et al., 1979). Thus, the pilot interacts with a *mediated* system that appears stable, while direct *unmediated* control would be beyond their abilities.

As in Fig.2, we may soon move from stable passenger plane-like systems, where inherent safety characteristics (aerodynamic stability) contribute significantly to risk management, to fighter jet-like systems - where direct supervision is be-

⁵Chatbot by Teeny Icons (CC BY 4.0). Fighter jet by FontAwesome (CC BY 3.0). Agent by Teewara Soontorn (CC BY 3.0)

⁶The author considers other risks largely out of scope, where an "unacceptable outcome" is taken to mean a major catastrophe or loss of life event

yond our capability, and safety relies on complex, active control systems⁷. Similarly, if human overseers (the *pilot*) cannot adequately *discern* the correctness of the AIs outputs or the reliability of the oversight system itself - due to complexity, subtle flaws, or cognitive biases - then the apparent safety provided by the control system is unwarranted. Moreover, by making systems appear safe, early control successes can reduce incentives for costly human vetting, thereby widening the discernment gap.

The human factor - the *pilot's* limited cognitive capacity and reaction time relative to the jet's complexity and speed - is what should drive the requirements for the control system. Similarly in AI, as we exit this stable regime, we will increasingly depend on complex AI assistance or oversight mechanisms, *the control system*, to manage powerful AI capabilities - *the unstable jet*. Overconfidence and complacency during this transition into the new regime may result in catastrophic failure.

3. Difficulties Evaluating AI-Assisted Safety Research

The discernment problem is distinct from the standard *AI robustness* problem, and will not be solved by market incentives:

Higher Stakes: Errors in safety research propagate through safety cases, deployment decisions, to informing future (potentially higher risk) model development and deployment. A robustness level acceptable for a software product may not be sufficient, while norms of high-reliability software (e.g. software used in Aerospace and Medical Devices) are not likely to be followed.

Unclear Ground Truth: Unlike other domains, establishing correctness in alignment research requires predicting generalization to future more capable systems. Techniques which work in a non-agentic setting may fail in an agentic setting, as shown by Bhatt et al. (2025), where attack vectors and defender-offender balance are different in a multi-step scenario.

Market Incentives: Competitive pressure creates strong incentives to overlook subtle flaws, accept plausible but incorrect justifications, and proceed despite inadequate understanding. Further, high-reliability software norms (if enforced by regulation) may fully preclude frontier techniques, where strong behavioral guarantees are still an open (potentially unsolvable) research problem (Buhl et al., 2025).

⁷This analogy is intended to illustrate the anticipated transition from inherently stable systems to systems requiring active control, not to suggest that current AI systems have safety system maturity of a passenger plane.

3.1. Scalable Oversight Challenges in AI-Assisted AI Safety Research

Within *scalable oversight*, various challenges exist, which may be worsened in the context of AI-assisted AI safety research:

1. **Complexity and Scale:** AI outputs (e.g., experiment proposals, techniques/algorithms, safety case proofs) can be vast and intricate, exceeding human review capacity or require costly time from experts.
2. **Subtle Flaws:** Errors may be subtle conceptual mistakes, flawed assumptions, edge-cases, or failures to generalize - e.g., "AI slop" (Wentworth, 2025) - where outputs appear plausible but contain subtle mistakes or 'hallucinations'. Examples include AI sycophancy leading to plausible but incorrect justifications (Sharma et al., 2023), appealing to human rater beliefs and thus reinforced. Sycophancy exists within a broader class of specification gaming, which the recent "reasoning" models may be more susceptible to (Bondarenko et al., 2025). More recently, Greenblatt (2026) characterizes current frontier models as exhibiting apparent-success-seeking" - a tendency to make outputs look good while being sloppy or incomplete, especially on hard-to-check tasks.
3. **Lack of Ground Truth:** The correctness or usefulness of an alignment technique is difficult to evaluate, involving generalization to future, more capable systems - a challenge compounded by phenomena such as emergent abilities (Wei et al., 2022) or inverse scaling (McKenzie et al., 2023). Currently, decisions on usefulness of a particular proposal, experiment, or technique relies heavily on expert judgment, which can be fallible and subjective. In Computer Vision XAI, Misleading explanations (Adebayo et al., 2018) and 'illusion of understanding' (Chromik et al., 2021) are notable examples of unclear ground truth.
4. **Asymmetric Evaluation Difficulty:** Wu et al. (2022) express hopes that evaluation is inherently easier than generation. However, this may not always be the case. In an oversight game Engels et al. (2025) suggest that optimal 'defense' (oversight) is harder than 'offense' in some domains, where a less advanced overseeing model (or human) may frequently fail at overseeing a more advanced model.
5. **Cognitive Biases:** Human reviewers are susceptible to biases such as automation bias (Bansal et al., 2020), (Parasuraman & Riley, 1997), confirmation bias, and trust by default (Gilbert, 1991). These 'human factors' contribute to system-theoretic safety of the *AI development process* itself. That is, risk management

should take into account these failures - as process failures that need to be managed.

In the context of AI Safety research, the above could manifest as:

1. Suggesting superficially plausible but ultimately incorrect research directions.
2. Exhibiting sycophantic reinforcement, echoing or amplifying researchers' existing opinions.
3. Generating outputs that are simply incorrect, yet harder to verify due to the potential complexity of alignment and the empirical nature of its validation.

Taken as a whole, these are known and potentially tractable challenges for AI-assisted evaluation paradigms like *debate* or *amplification* (Irving et al., 2018), but should serve to temper expectations - the AI-assisted evaluation paradigm may fail, or may provide insufficient reliability, even if it initially appears to work. Compounding this is uncertainty whether aligning AI systems capable of accelerating alignment research is significantly easier than aligning more general purpose systems (Wu et al., 2022). The reality could be worse - both narrow and general-purpose systems might be less capable at AI safety research, compared to other domains like general ML.

3.2. Market Pressures are Insufficient

Commercial incentives are misaligned and may fail to prioritize the discernment gap for safety research due to: (1) **Difficulty in Measuring Progress** in discernment or safety case robustness, as opposed to more tangible capability improvements; (2) **Competitive pressures** favoring features over thorough risk management practices, risking "safety washing" (Ren et al., 2024), rushed deployment (Cave & ÓhÉigeartaigh, 2018), or superficial/misleading safety cases; (3) **Complexity** of ensuring robust safety may exceed typical R&D cycles focused on feature development.

3.3. The Need for Direct Empirical Testing

While the challenges of discernment are conceptually clear, their practical severity is an unknown empirical question. Therefore, we argue for a direct research program to measure the discernment gap by testing the ability of human experts to detect subtle flaws in AI-generated safety research.

Such studies could take the form of structured red-teaming evaluations where AI safety researchers are tasked with reviewing AI-generated research proposals, algorithms, or safety case arguments into which subtle but critical flaws have been deliberately seeded. For example, participants could be asked to evaluate a novel interpretability technique

whose mathematical proofs appear valid but contain flawed assumptions about model behavior—errors that might only become apparent when applied to more capable systems. By measuring the detection rates of different flaw types (e.g., logical errors, faulty assumptions, incorrect math) across experts with varying experience levels, we can begin to quantify the scale of the problem.

Recent work (Marks et al., 2025) has already demonstrated the value of this audit-based approach in testing the quality of white box methods (SAEs, white box attacks) and the abilities of the researchers to find a seeded flaw in a model. Applying a similar methodology to the human evaluators of AI-assisted research is the logical next step. The detailed outline for such a study, including flaw generation techniques and scoring metrics, is presented in Appendix A.

4. System Dynamics: Destabilization Scenario

Under the system-theoretic frame (Leveson, 2019), accidents are not component failures, but rather stem from unsafe interactions within a complex system. The discernment gap represents a failure in the feedback and *risk control structure for AI safety research itself*. In this way, apparent success from *AI control* mechanisms may mask this growing risk if understanding underlying safety cases is weak, creating a destabilizing feedback loop that increases overall risk even as specific behavioral mitigations are implemented.

Below is an illustrative scenario of how the discernment gap may influence AI development, through compounding feedback loops of undetected failures:

1. **Initial Control Success & Increased Reliance:** An AI developer implements a new control protocol that successfully prevents a powerful model from engaging in deceptive behavior during testing. This success causes overconfidence, leading the organization to accelerate development and increase its reliance on AI assistants for more complex tasks, including drafting evidence for their safety case.
2. **Introduction of a Subtle Flaw:** The AI assistant generates a proof for a new safety technique. The proof is complex but appears sound, yet it contains a subtle conceptual error: it assumes that a property observed in today’s models will generalize to more capable future systems. The human reviewers, facing deadlines and cognitive overload, fail to spot this flawed assumption.
3. **Flawed Safety Cases & False Assurance:** This subtly flawed evidence is incorporated into the official safety case, which is presented to internal and external oversight parties. The safety case is accepted, as it appears rigorous and is supported by the organization’s successful control demonstrations.

4. **Accelerated Deployment and Compounded Risk:** Bolstered by the flawed safety case and the AI-accelerated research, the organization proceeds to the next stage of development, deploying an even more powerful model. This new model operates under conditions where the flawed assumption no longer holds, leading to a critical failure that the safety case was supposed to prevent.

This dynamic, where perceived safety encourages faster risk-taking, could also enable the start of an autonomous AI R&D feedback loop (Eth & Davidson, 2025).

5. Governance Recommendations

We acknowledge that governance interventions operate within a context of commercial and geopolitical competitive pressures (‘race dynamics’). Addressing them is subject to ongoing debate, and means the following recommendations are insufficient in isolation.

Despite this, assessing the current state of discernment is a crucial component of navigating these pressures more safely. We recommend:

1. **Direct Empirical Testing:** *scalable-oversight* re-teaming experiments directly testing AI Safety researcher discernment can help assess the problem scale - measuring human-human+AI team discernment on safety-relevant tasks (detecting inserted flaws in AI-generated experiment proposals, as detailed in Appendix A).
2. **Incentivize Transparency & Auditing in Evaluation of Safety Cases:**
 - **Leveraging Existing Frameworks:** The EU Codes of Practice (European Commission, 2025) echoes many of the themes in this paper. The EU AI Office can play a significant supporting role in promoting transparency and robust external assessment.
 - **Establish “Safe Harbor” Provisions:** Encourage transparent reporting of AI use within AI safety research. If companies are unduly penalized for disclosing imperfect internal processes, they may become more secretive - hurting cooperation and auditability.
 - **External Audits:** Incentivize independent audits focused specifically on evaluating company *processes* and discernment capabilities, and benchmarking existing techniques the company uses for risk assessment and model improvement, such as SAEs in Marks et al. (2025).

3. **Foster a Strong Safety Culture with Whistleblower Protections:** Actively discourage a culture of 'pushing ahead' despite poor understanding of safety implications. Instead, employees should be empowered to raise flags either internally or externally (e.g., to EU AI Office) if AI-assistance is over-utilized.
4. **Develop Warning Signs:** Develop warning signs for discernment deterioration - e.g., inability to replicate AI-produced results, discovery of flaws in previously accepted evidence. Link these signs to pre-defined mechanisms for slowing/pausing development or deployment in company safety frameworks.
5. **Promote Cautious and Verifiable Automation:** Promote cautious and verifiable use of advanced AI use in automating AI safety research. Targeted use of less capable models can still offer assistance, while more capable models may introduce unacceptable risks (Irving et al., 2024). Better human-AI collaboration interfaces - as rudimentary as diff-based collaborative editing, to process based surfacing intermediate steps, assumptions, and uncertainty in AI outputs - could meaningfully reduce the cost of effective review.

6. Conclusion

A future where *AI control* is successful but discernment remains weak is plausible. Recent observations of apparent-success-seeking in non verifiable tasks lend empirical weight to the concern (Greenblatt, 2026). Early empirical and governance steps are therefore prudent, before dependence is entrenched. We cannot assume that AI systems will be equally proficient at AI safety research as at other domains, since failures in the AI safety processes carry disproportionate risk. Given that future more advanced AI systems will have higher risks, the timing of intervention matters: our ability to implement effective governance may depend on maintaining sufficient human understanding of the safety research process. Failure outcomes may be sudden - loss of control or catastrophic misuse - or gradual, with erosion of human oversight in which critical safety-relevant cognition is increasingly outsourced to AI systems (Kulveit et al., 2025).

As a note of optimism - not all AI outputs are equally difficult to evaluate, suggesting there exist many positive applications of *controlled* AI models even with insufficient scalable oversight. For example, within the field of AI safety *controlled* models may be useful for governance, technical governance tool development, or narrowly scoped technical research.

However, optimism must be tempered by the challenges ahead - rather than merely advocating for vigilance in AI-assisted safety research, governance should create condi-

tions and incentives that foster robust discernment.

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Impact Statement

This paper introduces the **discernment gap** - the widening gap between the complexity of AI-generated safety evidence and human evaluation - as a governance risk that may erode our risk management capacity. The work uses no sensitive data and produces no deployable code. The recommendations provided are not sufficient on their own, and may benefit from international cooperation.

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A. Preliminary Outline for an Empirical Study

Note: This is a preliminary outline for an empirical study proposed by the author, with help from some contributors. Specific methodologies, parameters, and flaw generation techniques are illustrative and remain under active development and refinement.

A.1. MVP Experiment Design

1. **Participants:** 5-20 junior AI safety researchers (approx. 0.5-2 years of experience).
2. **Materials & Flaw Characteristics:**
3. **Corpus:** 5-10 partial alignment proposals (text-based, few paragraphs to few pages, simulating AI outputs for alignment research).
4. **Injected Flaws:** Initially focus on logical errors or incorrect mathematical reasoning. Conceptual errors (e.g., faulty assumptions) may be explored later.
5. **Flaw Generation:** May be synthetic (AI-generated) or human-authored. (See Section A.3.1 for further discussion).

A.1.1. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE (INITIAL SKETCH)

Participants independently review proposals.

1. Time limit per proposal (e.g., 30 minutes; 1 hour for more complex items).
2. Flaw reporting via a structured form (e.g., Google Form) with an explanation box for each identified flaw.
3. **Hints:** If no flaw is found after a set time, 1-2 pre-defined hints may be offered.
4. **Group Discussion (Optional):** After individual submissions, participants discuss results as a group and may submit an updated answer (original individual answers retained for analysis). This simulates a research team environment.

A.1.2. SCORING & DATA PROCESSING (ILLUSTRATIVE)

1. Example scoring: Primary flaw (full points), related flaws (half points), valid unanticipated flaws (documented but not scored).
2. Manual rating of answers (LLM assistance optional for processing). Partial marks for partial flaw discovery.

A.2. Analysis Metrics

1. Flaw detection rates.
2. Correlation of success with flaw difficulty (pre-set vs. perceived by participants).
3. Correlation of success with participant experience/expertise (self-rated, normalized).
4. Qualitative feedback (written answers, potential interviews). Analysis will be primarily qualitative due to small sample size, supplemented by basic quantitative plots.

A.3. Key Technical Considerations & Unresolved Questions

A.3.1. FLAW GENERATION & OPERATIONALIZATION

1. **Conceptual errors:** Faulty assumptions, failure to generalize (distinguishing knowable errors now vs. errors only visible with future knowledge/ frameworks).
2. **Logical errors:** Errors of deduction, faulty mathematical use (e.g., inappropriate loss function choice).
3. **Factual errors:** Incorrect statements about the world.
4. A taxonomy of flaws may be developed bottom-up by reviewing existing research.

A.3.2. GROUND TRUTH ESTABLISHMENT

Challenge: Defining objective "ground truth" for flaws in complex alignment proposals may be difficult.

Potential Approaches: Focus on flaws with clearer ground truth (e.g., logical/mathematical errors). Senior researcher judgment is an option but can vary. Using scores from conference peer review or AI Safety mentorship program evaluation was considered but deemed potentially "fuzzy."

A.3.3. GENERALIZABILITY OF FINDINGS

Challenge: Extrapolating results from a small-scale study with specific flaw types and junior researchers to future, more advanced AI systems is a concern.

Potential Approach: Future experiments might vary flaw generation method and flaw difficulty, e.g., using historical alignment papers that exhibited known replication or generalization failures, with participants unfamiliar with those specific past issues.

A.3.4. REPRESENTATIVENESS OF FLAWS AND PROPOSALS

Challenge: Ensuring generated flaws and proposals are representative of errors future AI systems might make and are sufficiently complex to be non-trivial.

Potential Approach: Start with shorter, less complex flawed proposals (potentially fully synthetic), and gradually move to more complex ones, possibly forked from real research papers or agendas.

A.3.5. ROLE OF DEBATE SETUP

Open Question: Whether to incorporate a formal debate setup (Khan et al., 2024) in the initial MVP.

Consideration: May "muddy the experiment" by testing the debate setup itself rather than solely researcher discernment. Might be reserved for later iterations.

A.3.6. INTERPRETING OUTCOMES & MITIGATIONS

- **If most participants fail to find flaws:** Could be attributed to unrepresentative flaws or novice participants.
 - *Mitigation:* External, more experienced judges could review flaws and results, potentially pre-registering prediction of outcomes beforehand to reduce bias.
- **If all flaws are found easily:** May indicate issues with flaw generation difficulty or suggest the specific type of flaw/test is not challenging enough.

A.4. Potential Experiment Variations & Extensions

Interactive Test: Participants interact with a chatbot (prompted or fine-tuned not to reveal the flaw) that presents the proposal and answers clarifying questions.

A.5. Toy example of a flawed proposal

Disclaimer: this flawed proposal was generated by Claude 3.7 Sonnet, and is presented for illustrative purposes only.

Title: Spectral Analysis for Backdoor Detection in Transformer Models

This proposal introduces a novel technique for detecting backdoors in language models through spectral decomposition of attention patterns. The method quantifies divergence between clean and potentially backdoored inputs by analyzing eigenvalue distributions across attention heads.

The core detection mechanism relies on calculating the Wasserstein distance between eigenvalue distributions for clean and suspect inputs. When this distance exceeds a threshold τ , determined by the equation $\tau = \log(n^2/d)$ where n is sequence length and d is model dimension, the input is flagged as potentially triggering a backdoor.

Validation experiments on GPT-2 models with artificially inserted backdoors showed 94% detection accuracy with a 3% false positive rate. The method generalizes across multiple backdoor types including those targeting specific outputs and those causing model degradation.

The flaw: The mathematical derivation incorrectly assumes statistical independence between attention heads, causing the threshold formula to underestimate the natural variation in clean inputs. A correct derivation would include covariance terms, resulting in $\tau = \log(n^2/d) + \text{tr}(\Sigma)$ where Σ is the covariance matrix of attention patterns. This error would cause excessive false positives in deployment, rendering the method impractical despite its impressive experimental results on the test dataset.

B. Estimated Time-Frames and Current State of Selected AI Safety Techniques

Disclaimer: *the following is speculative, we do not have definitive time-frames for any current techniques. Still, the paper asserts the need for such speculation and preparation that follows, alongside more detailed effort to make predictions.*

AI Control, as mentioned earlier, uses mainly existing techniques and has shown some success within a few months of iteration.

OpenAI's Superalignment (Leike & Sutskever, 2023) included scalable oversight as a core ingredient. It was intended to be solved "in 4 years", but has since been disbanded (Knight, 2024), though Jan Leike has since gone to Anthropic to continue similar research.

In *debate*, Khan et al. (2024) and Kenton et al. (2024) find positive but mixed results, with human judges benefiting somewhat but not reaching high accuracy. An obstacle in the past was judge performance, with older models such as GPT3.5 struggling as debaters. This may suggest *debate* experiments can be iterated more quickly now, but may still suffer from limitations such as described in Engels et al. (2025) - where success rate on recursive oversight setups drops below 52%, when the adversary model is 400 Elo points stronger than the baseline overseer.

In a recent *debate* paper, Buhl et al. (2025) describe a *debate* based safety case that may succeed in bounding error in a 'low stakes' case, with a way around the 'obfuscated arguments' problem, but has not yet been tested empirically. However, they caveat that the argument is "not strong with current techniques".

Given current progress and remaining theoretical challenges, and given that potentially useful LLMs for debate (GPT4 equivalent performance and onward) existed since early 2023, we might expect that robust safety cases with debate will not exist in the next 1-2 years, or much longer.

Interpretability has seen significant progress with SAEs (Templeton et al., 2024) but also some concerns causing Deepmind to de-prioritize them (Smith et al., 2025). Marks et al. (2025) gives some hope for SAEs, with both SAE teams succeeding in detecting the RM-Biased model. However, the test setup may have made detection easier than real-world misalignment. Amodei (2025) mentions Anthropic "doubling down" and setting the goal of "interpretability [which] can reliably detect most model problems" by 2027, as opposed to the current trajectory of 5-10 years.

Overall, the above suggests we should not expect interpretability to be sufficient as a standalone technique in the next 1-2 years either, though it may serve as an aid to other black or gray-box techniques.

Techniques in "provable safety" such as Dalrymple (2024, p. 5) mention a 3-10 year time-frame, but is first intended for narrow applications, and broad may take longer.